

BIODT
biodiversitydigitaltwin

Project Title	Biodiversity Digital Twin for Advanced Modelling, Simulation and Prediction Capabilities
Project Acronym	BioDT
Project Number	101057437
Type of project	RIA - Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-TECH-01-01
Starting date of Project	1 June 2022
Ending date of Project	31 May 2025
Duration of the project	36 months
Website	www.biodt.eu

D5.1 Pilot Service to Open Up FAIR Semantic Mappings for FDO

Work Package	WP5 Improving Quality of Data, Workflows and Models through FAIR Principles
Task	T5.2 Pilot FAIR semantic mappings and provide them as a service
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Version	V1.0
Due Date	31/05/2024
Submission Date	31/05/2024

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	SEN: Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Funded by
the European Union

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	19/04/2024	Jonas Grieb	ToC
0.2	07/05/2024	Jonas Grieb, Claus Weiland, Alexander Wolodkin	Initial draft
0.3	13/05/2024	Claus Weiland, Jonas Grieb	Revised version including peer reviewer's suggestions
0.4	28/05/2024	Jonas Grieb	Final version
1.0	31/05/2024	Gabriela de Paula Souza Zuquim (CSC), Jenni Poutanen (CSC)	Submission-ready version incorporating BioDT Project Management Office (PMO) editorial changes

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
DEDL	Destination Earth Data Lake
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
DTR	The EOSC Data Type Registry, which enables registration of PID metadata elements as data types and their subsequent reuse to build complex data types.
eLTER	Integrated European Long-Term Ecosystem, critical zone and socio-ecological Research
ENVO	The Environment Ontology (ENVO) is an ontology within the framework of the Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry to describe environmental systems, components, and processes.
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud is an emerging cross-disciplinary infrastructure to foster seamless and FAIR-compliant access to and reuse of European research data.
FAIR	Guidelines to improve and foster reuse of digital research assets with respect to the four foundational principles Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability.
FDO	FAIR Digital Objects are abstracted data objects encapsulating content, descriptive metadata and globally resolvable and persistent identifiers in compliance with the FAIR principles.
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility

JSON-LD	JSON-LD is a syntax to serialize Linked Data in JSON and can therefore be used as an RDF syntax
Mapping	Tuple of two entities from two semantic artefacts and their relation
MSCR	The EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry supports publishing, discovery and retrieval of metadata alignments/crosswalks and provides functionality for conversions combining crosswalks.
OWL	Web Ontology Language (OWL) is a decision Logic-based language enabling formal modelling of types of resources and their relationships.
pDT	Prototype Digital Twins (within the scope of BioDT) combine and encapsulate biodiversity and environmental data streams from European Research Infrastructures and advanced modelling techniques in digital objects to enable comprehensive simulations and decision-making.
PID	Persistent identifier
RDF	The Resource Description Framework is a standard data model of the Semantic Web to model resources and statements about those as triples in a knowledge graph.
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
SEMAF	EOSC secretariat co-creation project to specify a flexible framework to create a flexible semantic mapping framework embedded in a service ecosystem leveraging on FAIR Digital Object technology.
SKOS	The Simple Knowledge Organisation System is a formal framework for the development of knowledge organization systems like thesauri and controlled vocabularies for the Semantic Web.
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings
UI	User interface

Keywords

Biodiversity, Digital Twin, Modelling, Semantics, Ontology Mapping, SSSOM, FDO, Resource Description framework, Web Ontology Language, EOSC

Disclaimer

The BioDT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101057437 (<https://doi.org/10.3030/101057437>). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

The following deliverable summarizes the steps to integrate mapping.bio, a tool to create and curate FAIR semantic mappings, into BioDT's FAIR service architecture. Mapping.bio was designed by building on an EOSC study proposing a framework to generate, document and publish mappings and crosswalks under the label "Flexible Semantic Mapping Framework" (SEMAF). The tool is implemented as a lightweight web service to visually create mappings using an intuitive user interface and to store these mappings in compliance with the "Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings" (SSSOM) as FAIR-compliant digital objects (FDOs) in a repository. The FDOs build on web-centric specifications such as RO-Crate (lightweight packaging of research outputs), schema.org/ Bioschemas (structured metadata) and FAIR Signposting (web linking of digital objects) which work effectively together to comprise machine-actionable data units suited for exchange and reuse of semantic mappings within and across federated data spaces such as EOSC and the Destination Earth Data Lake.

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1. Introduction

Intensifying anthropogenic influences on the environment such as extensive land use, wide ranging deforestation and water shortage due to competing uses are deeply impacting climate, habitats as well as their complex interplay (Hurr et al., 2020). These changes are compromising the ability of ecosystems to produce and supply essential services for economic and social systems.

These considerable societal and environmental challenges highlight the importance of the development and expansion of large-scale prediction capabilities as well as the requirement of comprehensive pooling of available biodiversity data, which is envisioned in European data space projects such as the Destination Earth Data Lake (DEDL, Duatis Juarez et al. 2023). For the larger regions considered by DEDL, this scales up to high dimensional problems requiring the involvement of a set of methods like predictive modelling, image processing, time series analyses, classification and regression tasks.

Biodiversity Digital Twins (<https://biodt.eu/>) employs such methods to address major challenges for human well-being like spreading of invasive species, zoonotic disease outbreaks and threats to food security such as decreasing crop yields. BioDT mobilizes data and models from the biodiversity- and environmental-related Research Infrastructures DiSSCo, LifeWatch ERIC and eLTER, as well as from GBIF which use various semantic artefacts (typically vocabularies, lexicons, thesauri, ontologies) introducing requirements for semantic harmonization (Jonquet 2023).

To achieve semantic interoperability for the federation of services that will compose EOSC, the EOSC Interoperability Framework highlights semantic mappings as a key precondition for seamless sharing of information and knowledge to enable service users to interact towards mutually beneficial goals (Corcho et al 2021). Building on this work, a design study funded by the EOSC Secretariat refined the architectural constraints for an FDO-based framework to create, document and publish mappings and crosswalks linking different semantic artefacts within a particular scientific community and across scientific domains under the label of "Flexible Semantic Mapping Framework" (SEMAF, Broeder et al. 2021).

Within the scope of BioDT, mapping.bio was developed leveraging on SEMAF's design proposals to facilitate reading, visualization, and adding mappings in a graphical frontend and enable sharing and mobilization of mappings or crosswalks as FAIR Digital Objects (Wolodkin et al. 2023).

Major objective of this expanded report in continuation of the previous milestone reports focussing on the prototype of the user interface (M28, M29) is to outline the adjustment of the mapping service with the BioDT's FAIR Digital Object layer (T5.1) based on web-based FDOs (Soilent-Reyes et al. 2024).

2. Methodology

2.1. Recap: The mapping.bio Service

The web service *mapping.bio* was built to serve as a tool for curating and sharing FAIR semantic mappings. The service consists of a JavaScript-based frontend with a user interface (UI) and backend which serves as a repository for FAIR semantic mappings. The frontend is a single page application based on Vue 3¹, the CSS framework Bulma² and the library Oruga UI³. To handle the semantic technology stack involving the Resource

¹ <https://vuejs.org/>

² <https://bulma.io/>

³ <https://oruga-ui.com/>

Description Framework (RDF), Web Ontology Language (OWL) and Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM, Matentzoglou 2022) the JavaScript library `rdf.js`⁴ is used. The backend solution is based on the digital objects middleware CORDRA⁵ but includes several customizations to support the publication of the mappings as web-based FDOs. This will be explained in detail in section 3. In the following, the capabilities of the user interface of *mapping.bio* will be described.

2.1.1. Service Design

The main feature of *mapping.bio* is the mapping editor, which is the default view provided to the user when entering the website. The mapping editor view is displayed in Figure 1. In this section of the website, the user may upload two different vocabularies. Each terminology is parsed and visualized in a tree structure, which represents the usually hierarchical structure of terminologies, like OWL ontologies, RDFS vocabularies or taxonomies based on the semantic web standard SKOS⁶. Currently, loading terminologies in the different expressivity levels OWL, RDFS and SKOS (in different serialization formats) is supported, however it is required to select the expressivity of the terminology at the moment of uploading the file. The user can then establish mappings by connecting related terms from both terminologies and qualifying their relationship. The individual mappings are stored and can be curated in a table. After finishing the curation of mappings between both terminologies, the user may either store them in the underlying mapping repository or export the mappings in a variety of formats including CSV and a number of RDF serializations such as RDF/XML⁷, Turtle⁸, and as JSON-LD compliant with the SSSOM data model. When exporting or storing the current set of mappings, the user is required to fill in metadata fields which facilitate the findability and reusability of the mappings by others, e.g., when and by whom were the mappings created, in which context, and under which license are they shared.

Currently two export formats are supported: The Open Archives Initiative's Object Exchange and Reuse standard⁹ and SSSOM. When mappings are stored in the repository, the SSSOM standard is always used as will be explained in more detail in chapter 3. To be able to persist mappings in the repository, a user is required to log in. For the support of user management and authentication, we make use of an existing authentication and authorisation solution run by Senckenberg which is powered by the open-source software Keycloak¹⁰. This intermediate solution can be replaced in the future by any other authentication infrastructure which supports OAuth 2.0 standard (Hardt, 2012).

The second feature of *mapping.bio* is the discoverability of existing mappings that are stored in the mapping repository. For this, a view has been implemented to browse through existing mapping sets and display in a detailed view the metadata of the mapping set, as well as the individual mappings themselves in a dedicated landing page.

⁴ <https://rdf.js.org/>

⁵ <https://www.cordra.org/>

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-syntax-grammar/>

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

⁹ <https://www.openarchives.org/ore/>

¹⁰ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Mapping Editor

Relation	Source title	Source link	Target title	Target link	confidence (sssom)	Review (sssom)	Comment	
1	skos:							
2	skos:							

Load a 1-row mapping example
Load 5-row mapping example

Choose a mapping file
Show all mappings
Export

Select mapping relation:

skos:exactMatch

Add mapping

Choose a RDF/XML or TTL file... SKOS

درجة حرارة الهواء@ar x air temperature

- variable@en
- air temperature@en
- surface air temperature@en
- mean annual air temperature@en

Choose a RDF/XML or TTL file... OWL

temperature of air x air

- entity@en
 - continuant@en
 - specifically dependent continuant@en
 - quality@en
 - physical object quality
 - physical quality
 - temperature
 - temperature of environ...
 - temperature of air

Figure 1 – Screenshot of mapping.bio showing the mapping editor view which supports the curation of FAIR semantic mappings between two terminologies

2.1.2. Envisioned Users

We envision a typical *mapping.bio* user to be a researcher in the field of biodiversity or in a broader field of Earth System Science (ESS). The user interface (UI) of *mapping.bio* currently only is available in English, as this is the most common language used in research. The UI includes only limited explanations as the users are expected to be familiar with semantic web standards. Additionally, our assumption is that the user will access the service via a desktop or laptop computer, and consequently a mobile friendly user interface has not been prioritized during development. Also, accessibility for visually impaired users has not been considered at the current stage of development. The need for special colours, contrasts, or other options may be evaluated at a later step.

2.1.3. Open Issues

While substantial progress has been made in the development of *mapping.bio* in comparison to the prototype, a few open issues remain which require further implementation effort in the future. This includes a currently limited functionality in editing existing mapping sets which have been stored previously in the repository. Additionally, the upload of terminologies in the mapping editor may take longer when the terminology is very large (also depending on the hardware of the system which is used to access *mapping.bio*, since the terminology is processed in-memory in the browser), thus having a negative effect on the user experience. Sizes of individual terminologies vary greatly, e.g., smaller ones might consist of only 10 to 20 classes (SOSA), whereas others have several thousand classes (ENVO), which requires more processing capacity to index and build the tree structure for visualization. In order to provide an overview on this topic, a few representative terminologies from different levels of expressivity have been tested with the current implementation of *mapping.bio*. The result is presented in Table 1.

Ontology name	Expressivity	Download	Approximate loading time
ENVO	owl	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/EnvironmentOntology/envo/master/envo.owl	80 seconds
SWEET RealmLandCoastal	owl	https://raw.githubusercontent.com/ESIPFed/sweet/master/src/realmLandCoastal.ttl	2 seconds
GEMET	SKOS	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/latest/gemet.rdf.gz	130 seconds
DCAT	RDFS	https://github.com/w3c/dxwg/tree/gh-pages/dcat/rdf/dcat3.ttl	2 seconds
schema.org	RDFS	https://schema.org/version/latest/schemaorg-all-https.ttl	8 seconds
SOSA	owl	http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/	1 second

Table 1 – Overview of terminologies and loading times which have been successfully tested to load into the *mapping.bio* mapping editor

2.2. Webby FDOs with RO-Crate and FAIR Signposting

Several implementation paths are suitable to create FAIR Digital Objects involving for the most part (i) approaches based on Digital Object (DO, Kahn et al. 2006) architecture employing Handles and the Digital Object Interface Protocol (DOIP, DONA Foundation 2018) as a sound basis for representing information on the Internet, (ii) methods employing Linked Data (LD) and appropriate web technologies like RDF, OWL and SPARQL with a focus on querying and drawing inferences from data (Santos 2023), and (iii) hybrid schemes involving elements of both concepts supplemented by non-LD web techniques such as FAIR Signposting (Wilkinson 2024).

The interoperability layer of *mapping.bio* follows the later approach leveraging on a technology stack combining common web technologies involving RO-Crates¹¹ (lightweight packaging of research outputs along

¹¹ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate>

with metadata, Soiland-Reyes 2024), Bioschemas¹² (structured metadata, Gray 2017) and FAIR Signposting¹³ (van de Sompel 2023). FAIR Signposting makes use of linksets outlined by RFC8288¹⁴ which point to the landing page of a web resource plus typed relation (such as *item*, *cite-as*, *describedby*, MIME types etc) to a related resource depicting in this way the web topology of the resource in concern (corresponding to the FDO concept).

Combining these technologies enables the implementation of “webby” FDOs providing a way to capture multiple mappings as well as to version and attribute the mapped semantic artefacts (Figure 2).

Figure 2 – FAIR Signposting link relations employed in the context of FAIR semantic mappings visualized using the Chrome Plugin “Signposting Sniffing”¹⁵ (Soiland-Reyes 2024b). The link relations provide metadata like license and authorship, as well as a more comprehensive description as RO-Crate (“describedby”).

3. Results

3.1. Provision of FAIR Semantic Mappings

The *mapping.bio* pilot service includes various components to ensure interoperability and reusability of the provided FAIR Semantic Mappings. These components include the internal data model which is closely aligned to the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM), the publication of created mappings as FAIR Digital Objects with persistent identifiers (PIDs) and finally the enabling of the data discoverability for machine agents based on FAIR Signposting and RO-Crates.

Any mapping which is created in *mapping.bio* and persisted in the underlying FAIR Semantic Mapping repository is natively stored as a JSON-LD¹⁶ document which is compliant to the SSSOM standard (Matentzoglou et al. 2022). This recent standard has been developed to meet the need of sharing not only mappings between ontology terms but also descriptive metadata elements which qualify the mappings and allow for a reliable reuse of these. The SSSOM standard is published based on the modelling language

¹² <https://bioschemas.org>

¹³ <https://signposting.org>

¹⁴ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc8288>

¹⁵ <https://chromewebstore.google.com/detail/signposting-sniffing/pahanegeimljfcjogglnamnlgjpmbc>

¹⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld/>

LinkML¹⁷. This enables the maintainers to publish SSSOM in various formats at the same time, eg., in the form of Python dataclasses¹⁸, a JSON schema for validation¹⁹ and a JSON-LD context file²⁰. In the *mapping.bio* repository we make use of the provided JSON schema to ensure schema compliance of any deposited mapping set, while at the same time embedding the JSON-LD context to ensure that the stored digital objects return linked data in the form of the RDF serialization JSON-LD.

Since we envision that for the use in BioDT mainly pragmatic mappings between sets of terms from two different vocabularies will be needed, the central entity of *mapping.bio* is the mapping set entity. Mapping sets as container objects can be created and curated via the user interface and stored in the underlying repository. In order to provide the stored mapping sets as FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs), for each mapping set a persistent identifier (PID) is minted based on the global handle.net infrastructure (Sun et al., 2003). For minting the PIDs we make use of a local handle server and a dedicated prefix which is run by Senckenberg and registered in the global registry.

Additionally, to minting PIDs, we implemented the support of two different “flavors” of FDOs in the *mapping.bio* repository: On the one hand, we started creating a FDO profile for the type “MappingSet” which defines kernel attributes that every MappingSet instance should register at the handle system along with the PID to facilitate data findability to autonomous machine agents. On the other hand, we implement a recent other FDO flavor, currently named “webby FDOs” (Stian et al., 2023). This FDO flavor makes use of existing and established semantic web standards, like JSON-LD, Signposting and RO-Crates. The approach is aligned with the ongoing effort in WP5 to build an FDO layer to consolidate FAIR data designs of the research infrastructures (Task 5.1).

¹⁷ <https://linkml.io/>

¹⁸ https://github.com/mapping-commons/sssom/blob/master/src/sssom_schema/datamodel/sssom_schema.py

¹⁹ https://github.com/mapping-commons/sssom/blob/master/project/jsonschema/sssom_schema.schema.json

²⁰ https://github.com/mapping-commons/sssom/blob/master/src/sssom_schema/context/sssom_schema.context.jsonld

Figure 3 – Schematic overview of the information flow after requesting a PID of a mapping set in the mapping.bio repository: A normal request returns a HTTP redirect to the human-readable landing page for human agents. However, a machine agent which understands FAIR Signposting may interpret the Signposting HTTP headers and subsequently retrieve the machine-readable information of the mapping set from the linked RO-Crate. On the other hand, a machine agent that reads PID records according to the Digital Object Architecture-based FDO approach may interpret the key-value pairs in the PID record to retrieve the same information and access the original SSSOM representation of the mapping set if needed.

3.2. mapping.bio in Action: Creation of Mappings at the B-Cubed Hackathon

During the B-Cubed Hackathon “Hacking Biodiversity Data Cubes for Policy”²¹ from 02.04.2024 to 05.04.2024 the *mapping.bio* service was used within the project “Interoperable eLTER Standard Observation variables for Biosphere”. As part of this project an eLTER dataset was used to create a Biodiversity Data Cube. The goal was to provide interoperable annotations of the resulting data cube using the Environmental Ontology (ENVO)²² and by making use of existing semantic annotations of the original dataset. However, the original annotations had been created using the vocabulary “EnvThes - Thesaurus for long term ecological research, monitoring and experiments”²³. Hence, a set of pragmatic mappings between both vocabularies was required and the *mapping.bio* service provided both a practical interface for the curation as well as an infrastructure for the interoperable publication of these mappings.

²¹ <https://b-cubed.eu/b-cubed-hackathon>

²² <http://environmentontology.org>

²³ <http://vocabs.lter-europe.net/EnvThes/>

The result of this hackathon can be accessed under the following handle PID: [hdl:20.500.14269/4e636785b24b](https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14269/4e636785b24b). As illustrated in Figure 3, the persistent identifier forwards the requesting agent to the human-readable landing page (see Figure 4) of the mapping set instance. However, the machine-readable information of the FDO record can be accessed under: <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14269/4e636785b24b?noredirect>

The response of the human-readable landing page returns the FAIR Signposting-compliant relations to link the landing page to the machine-readable RO-Crate representation of the mapping set as well as to other contextual entities like the license or author information, e.g.:

```
curl -I "https://mapping.bio/mappingsets/20.500.14269/4e636785b24b"
```

returns:

```
Link: <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14269/4e636785b24b> ; rel="cite-as",
<https://mapping.bio/api/call?objectId=20.500.14269/4e636785b24b&method=getAsROCrate>; rel="describedby" ; type="application/ld+json" ;
profile="https://w3id.org/ro/crate", <CC BY 4.0> ; rel="license",
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1556-8750> ; rel="author",
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8876-1722> ; rel="author"
```


Figure 4 – Landing page of the mapping set created during the B-Cubed Hackathon

4. Conclusions and Outlook

A major objective of the *mapping.bio* service is the provision of a lightweight UI to facilitate the straightforward creation of pragmatic semantic mappings, i.e. mappings which are targeted at specific interoperability goals, supported by an intuitive usable user interface. The service additionally fosters the FAIRification of mappings by providing mapping sets as SSSOM-compliant FDOs without needing the user to work directly with the digital object.

Going significantly further than this, the original design study envisions a distributed system of federated mapping services (so-called SEMAF Registries; Broeder et al. 2021), which is able to reuse and integrate existing resources and tooling.

A promising development appears to be the integration of terminology services: As explained in section 2.1.3, a remaining issue of the *mapping.bio* user interface is the long processing time when large terminologies consisting of several thousand classes are being loaded in the mapping editor. A possible solution to this would be to implement a connector to terminology services like the Ontology Lookup Service²⁴ or the BioPortal²⁵. However, this would require beforehand an assessment of which terminology service is the most relevant one in the context of BioDT and an assessment of the compatibility of the corresponding programming interfaces (APIs).

Software systems for automatic matching of semantic artefacts (*matching systems*, Angermann 2017), are currently not integrated in *mapping.bio*. As already mentioned on other occasions (FAIR-IMPACT 2023), the major use case of *mapping.bio* are mappings in the form of ‘pragmatic translations’ between metadata descriptions and observation measurements and are thus often targeted at specific interoperability goals as described in section 3.2. Matching systems in contrast aim for a more complete determination of correspondences between semantic artefacts, e.g. in the context of the Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative (OAEI, Karam 2020). The integration of term recommendation based on the LogMap matching system (Jiménez-Ruiz 2011) is currently being tested, since LogMap supports real time user interaction during the matching process.

An aforementioned core concept of SEMAF is the further establishment of multiple SEMAF registries that form a federation. As a first step, *mapping.bio* will collaborate with the EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry²⁶ (MSCR) using MSCR as a federated registry and optionally as repository for selected mappings.

A further objective of this cooperation is to strengthen in this way the semantic interoperability between the parent projects BioDT and FAIRCORE4EOSC²⁷.

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²⁷ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

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